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UNITY: AN INCLUSIVE SPORTS AND WELLNESS COMPLEX

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Abstract. *This article examines the socio-cultural significance of recreation complexes and parks in the life of society. The development of modern recreation infrastructure is aimed at effectively organizing people's leisure time, strengthening their health, and improving their quality of life. The base of recreation complexes is an important part of the tourism and cultural industry. The article analyzes the system of various infrastructure, environmental, and aesthetic factors that create conditions for meeting people's leisure and spiritual needs. The article discusses the architectural and planning features of recreation parks, the harmony of natural and urban spaces, and the issues of environmental sustainability in recreational areas. The relevance of introducing innovative technologies and improving the service culture in accordance with the needs of modern society is noted. The study revealed the social, economic, and cultural effects of an effective organization of wellness complexes.*

Keywords: *Resorts, amusement parks, recreation, tourism, infrastructure, culture, ecology, urbanism, leisure, quality of life, social development, and innovation.*

The wellness recreation subsystem is an important aspect of the modern approach to leisure and recreation. It is based on natural complexes that provide favorable conditions for mass recreation both within cities and in the suburbs. These wellness and recreational complexes can be viewed not only as places for recreation, but also as one of the mechanisms for developing the tourism industry. In the context of globalization and increasing tourist flows, the development of transit tourism has become particularly relevant, especially since international transport corridors pass through our country. This opens up new prospects and opportunities for attracting tourists who want to enjoy the beauty of nature and unique cultural offerings.

Hunting and fishing tours are one of the most popular activities among tourists. These outdoor activities allow people to not only enjoy the beautiful scenery, but also experience the thrill of hunting or fishing. Additionally, horseback riding, boating, and cycling tours are becoming increasingly popular, as they provide an opportunity to engage in outdoor activities and explore the natural beauty of the area.

The formation of park spaces largely depends on their purpose and usage.

Multidisciplinary parks typically offer a wide range of recreational activities, which makes them attractive to diverse populations. In such parks, special zones can be allocated, each of which is designed for certain types of activities. These can be playgrounds for children, walking areas, places for cultural events, sports and recreation areas, entertainment and amusement areas, as well as administrative and economic areas.

Each of these zones has its own character, which corresponds to the purpose of the recreational environment. For example, children's parks are primarily designed as spaces for exploring nature and engaging in leisure activities. Here, children can not only play but also interact with nature and participate in sports and creative games. It is important that the layout and spatial organization of the children's park align with its intended use. This involves creating a safe and comfortable environment that protects children from the adverse effects of the urban environment. To achieve this, dense protective vegetation is established within the park boundaries, shielding children from noise and pollution.

Children's parks also have designated areas for different age groups, which allows for individual needs and interests of children to be taken into account. Functional areas for various activities are separated from each other by green spaces, creating a cozy and safe environment for play and relaxation.

Sports and recreation parks, on the other hand, are designed for physical culture and sports. They include both outdoor sports grounds and indoor sports facilities. A mandatory element of such parks is water bodies, which not only decorate the territory but also serve as dividers between sports facilities and the surrounding buildings, creating a protective barrier.

Exhibition parks typically combine the functions of showcasing achievements in various fields, such as art, science, or technology. They can serve as venues for exhibitions, fairs, and other events aimed at promoting cultural and scientific achievements. These parks become centers of attraction for people interested in various aspects of cultural life. Therefore, the creation and development of wellness and recreational complexes, as well as park spaces, is an important step towards improving the quality of life for citizens and attracting tourists. These spaces not only promote physical and emotional well-being, but also create opportunities for socializing, cultural exchange, and active leisure activities. It is important that such complexes are developed in a way that takes into account the needs of society and the characteristics of the environment, allowing for the most efficient use of natural resources and creating comfortable conditions for recreation and leisure activities.

Zoos are designed to allow people to meet animals and learn about their breathing. When creating a zoo, the layout of the animals is carefully considered, with them being grouped by species (such as mammals, birds, and reptiles), geographical origin (countries), and efforts made to recreate their natural habitats.

Botanical gardens (arbors) are extensive collections of plants that differ in the diversity of species and forms, which are used to create picturesque park compositions. In arbors, scientific work is carried out on the selection and introduction of new, promising plants for various purposes: landscaping, landscape design, industrial production, as well as for forestry and agriculture. Plants here are organized into artistically valuable decorative groups. Arbors perform several functions at once: scientific, educational and recreational.

Features of rural parks. Rural parks are often located in areas that are not suitable for development or active agriculture, such as river valleys, among rocks, or on steep slopes. Their main value lies in their natural beauty and the harmonious transitions between different elements of the

landscape. Therefore, when planning such parks, it is crucial to preserve and emphasize the visual connection between the park and the surrounding nature.

There are many old parks in rural areas that need to be restored, but they can still be used today. These old parks are usually located on the grounds of former estates and cover relatively small areas, ranging from 5 to 8 hectares.

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